

**DESIGN OF MICROCONTROLLER-BASED MODULAR POWER FACTOR
CORRECTION BOOST CONVERTER WITH SILICON CARBIDE
SEMICONDUCTOR MATERIALS**

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a design and simulation of power factor corrected microcontroller-based modular boost converter developed for a 2 kW load at a 600 V direct current output. In order to reduce switching losses and improve thermal performance, Silicon Carbide semiconductor devices were preferred over conventional silicon components throughout the power stage. The control approach adopted in the study is based on average current mode control, which was implemented on an ARM-based NUCLEO-G474RE microcontroller. A modular architecture was chosen because it allows the converter to be scaled toward higher power demands while also simplifying maintenance; since each module operates independently and can be replaced without affecting the rest of the system. The developed converter consists of theoretical power stage calculations, LTspice circuit simulations, control algorithm design, and prototype fabrication, respectively. According to the simulation results, when a 220 V alternating current input powers the system, the output voltage reaches approximately 600 V. During these simulations, it was observed that a synchronized sinusoidal waveform was maintained. This indicates that effective power factor correction was achieved. As the control algorithm, a dual-loop scheme was implemented in which the outer loop regulates the output voltage and the inner loop shapes the input current. The driver stage was implemented using the UCC21520DW isolated dual-channel integrated circuit and was experimentally verified at 20 kHz with a 15 V output amplitude; this confirmed that the isolated pulse-width modulation signal was correctly transmitted to the switching element.

Keywords: Average current mode control, LTspice simulation, Power Factor Correction, Silicon Carbide

1. INTRODUCTION

The importance of energy efficiency in industrial power electronics applications is growing. Nonlinear loads draw harmonic currents from the frequency multiples of the power grid. This increases reactive power demand, reduces efficiency, and exacerbates power quality issues [1]. Bringing the power factor the ratio of active power to reactive power closer to unity is one of the fundamental methods for mitigating these effects. For this reason, international standards such as IEC 61000-3-2 and IEEE 519 have made power factor correction (PFC) a mandatory requirement for most medium- and high-power converters. Among active PFC topologies, continuous conduction mode (CCM) plays a significant role for medium- and high-power boost converters rated at 400W and above [1]. CCM is important in PFC topologies because a constant input current keeps conducted electromagnetic interference low. Increases in switching frequency and power increase the switching losses of the switching device. This increase is one of the key factors limiting the design. Therefore, PFC converters designed with soft-switching and wide-bandgap semiconductors prioritize minimizing losses to improve efficiency [2]. Silicon carbide (SiC) circuit components play a crucial role precisely at this point. Compared to their silicon based alternatives, they offer lower switching and conduction losses. Their behavior at high temperatures is more stable. These advantages have made the use of SiC components increasingly popular in designs where such efficiency is sought.

In the literature, various approaches for PFC exist at both the converter and microcontroller levels. In one study, a method capable of correcting the power factor using average current control was proposed for a multi-phase CCM PFC boost converter. While the power factor was maintained above 94% over a wide load range, the IEC 61000-3-2 Class D limits were also met [3]. In another study, a systematic control loop design method using an average-switch model was developed for a 1.6 kW boost PFC converter, demonstrating that the dynamic behavior of nested voltage and current loops could be pre-calculated [4]. In a prototyped example, a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controlled active boost PFC converter was driven by an Arduino-based microcontroller; the controller parameters were first tuned in the MATLAB/Simulink environment and then validated on the hardware [5]. In a study prepared using a simpler approach, the power factor of inductive loads was improved by engaging a static capacitor bank via a PIC microcontroller [6]. In another 2 kW PFC study, it was reported that gate oxide degradation and threshold voltage shift were observed in SiC switching elements operated under accelerated stress conditions within the converter [7]. Based on these studies, this developed system presents the design of a 2 kW nominal power, microcontroller-based, modular PFC boost converter with a 600 V direct current (DC) output. This converter combines three features that are typically addressed separately: SiC semiconductor devices in the power stage, an average current-mode control law and a modular architecture that allows independent units to be connected in parallel to enable scalability to higher power levels and facilitate maintenance. The control algorithm is running on an ARM-based NUCLEO-G474RE microcontroller. The work reported here covers the theoretical power stage design, closed-loop circuit simulation, gate driver design, and experimental validation.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

The designed converter was developed by following a four-step methodology. Theoretical design of the power stage and selection of converters components, closed-loop simulation of controller in the LTspice environment, design and fabrication of the printed circuit board (PCB) for the isolated gate driver, implementation of the control algorithm as firmware on the STM32 microcontroller. The hardware consists of a full bridge rectifier, a boost power stage built with SiC components, isolated gate driver, and a microcontroller running the average current mode controller. Each stage is described in the following subsections.

2.1. System Architecture and Power Stage Design

Figure 1 shows the topology of the PFC boost converter. The single-phase mains voltage is rectified by a full-bridge diode rectifier and applied to the boost stage, which consists of the boost inductor (L), a SiC switching device, a SiC boost diode and the output capacitor (C). The controller drives the switching device so that the input current follows the rectified sinusoidal voltage while the output voltage is regulated at its set point. SiC devices were selected for the switch and the diode because of their lower switching losses and better thermal performance at high voltage compared with silicon parts (Figure 2); the same operating regime has, however, motivated reliability studies of SiC MOSFETs under continuous PFC operation [7].

Figure 1. PFC boost converter topology with full-bridge rectifier and controller.

Figure 2. SiC MOSFET and diode examples for high-voltage applications [8,9].

The power stage was configured to provide a nominal output power of 2 kW at a regulated DC output voltage of 600 V, powered by a 220 V root-mean-square single-phase mains supply. After full wave rectification, the peak voltage applied to the boost stage is approximately 311 V. The switching frequency is adjusted to 20 kHz. While the average output current is at rated load the output current is 3.33 A, higher of the boost action and settles near 6.4 A. The steady-state duty cycle follows from the boost relationship in Equation (1). Duty cycle value is 0.48 at the nominal operating point, and the equivalent load resistance is obtained from Equation (2).

$$D = 1 - \frac{V_{in}}{V_{out}} \quad (1)$$

$$R = \frac{V_{out}}{I_{out}} \quad (2)$$

The inductance of the boost inductor has been specified to keep the CCM at its nominal load. Allowing for a peak to peak current ripple of approximately 20% of the average inductor current and evaluating Equation (3) at the nominal operating point yields the minimum inductance value. A standard value of 15 mH has been selected to provide a margin against magnetic saturation and to reduce core losses. With this value, the actual current ripple remains close to 0.5 A, and continuous conduction is ensured throughout the operating range.

$$L_{min} = \frac{V_{in} \cdot D}{\Delta I_L \cdot f_s} \quad (3)$$

The capacitance value of the output capacitor was calculated using Equation (4). The peak to peak output voltage ripple was set to 2% of the desired output voltage. A 2000 μ F capacitor was selected to compensate for the equivalent series resistance of the capacitors and to ensure energy storage during load transients. The final power stage schematic, including the calculated component values, is shown in Figure 3.

$$C_{min} = \frac{D}{R \cdot \frac{\Delta V_o}{V_o} \cdot f_s} \quad (4)$$

Figure 3. Designed power-stage schematic of the boost converter with calculated component values.

2.2. Control System Design

The converter is regulated by an average current mode control law with two interacting loops, as shown in Figure 4. The outer voltage loop samples the output voltage, compares it to the reference, and processes the error via a PI compensator; the output of this compensator determines the amplitude of the reference current. The inner current loop forces the inductor current to match this reference; this reference is shaped by the corrected line voltage to ensure the input current remains sinusoidal and in phase with the supply. The output of the current compensator is compared with a saw-tooth carrier to generate the PWM signal that drives the switch [3,4].

Figure 4. Average current mode control algorithm block diagram with dual-loop structure.

The control algorithm is executed on an ARM Cortex-based NUCLEO-G474RE microcontroller (Figure 5). The simulated controller maps directly onto the firmware. The two PI loops run inside the analog to digital converter (ADC) direct memory access conversion complete interrupt at the 20 kHz switching rate, and the PWM duty cycle is updated every switching cycle.

```

while (1)
{
    /* Control runs entirely in the ADC DMA callback below. */
}

/* USER CODE BEGIN 4 */
/* Fires at 20 kHz, once all three channels are converted. */
void HAL_ADC_ConvCpltCallback(ADC_HandleTypeDef *hadc)
{
    if (hadc->Instance != ADC1) return;

    float vout = adc_buf[0] * VOUT_GAIN;
    float iL   = (adc_buf[1] - IL_OFFSET) * IL_GAIN;
    float vin  = adc_buf[2] * VIN_GAIN;

    float vin_norm = vin / VIN_PEAK; /* mains template, 0.1 */
    if (vin_norm > 1.0f) vin_norm = 1.0f;

    float duty = pfc_step(vout, iL, vin_norm);
    __HAL_TIM_SET_COMPARE(&htim1, TIM_CHANNEL_1,
        (uint32_t)(duty * (htim1.Init.Period + 1)));
}
/* USER CODE END 4 */

```

Figure 5. ADC/DMA interrupt control running the control loop at 20 kHz.

The high-speed ADC samples the output voltage and the inductor current, while the timer and interrupt peripherals provide the deterministic timing required for current-loop stability (Figure 6). The firmware was developed in the STM32CubeIDE environment [10].

```

#include "pfc_control.h"

static float vint = 0.0f; /* voltage loop integrator */
static float iint = 0.0f; /* current loop integrator */

static float clampf(float x, float lo, float hi)
{
    return (x < lo) ? lo : ((x > hi) ? hi : x);
}

void pfc_reset(void)
{
    vint = 0.0f;
    iint = 0.0f;
}

float pfc_step(float vout, float iL, float vin_norm)
{
    /* Outer voltage loop -> current amplitude */
    float verr = PFC_VREF - vout;
    vint += PFC_KIV * clampf(verr, -100.0f, 100.0f) * PFC_TS;
    float amp = clampf((verr * PFC_KPV + vint) * 25.0f, 0.0f, 16.0f);

    /* Shape by the mains -> current reference (this gives PFC) */
    float iref = amp * vin_norm;

    /* Inner current loop -> duty cycle */
    float ierr = iref - iL;
    iint += PFC_KIC * clampf(ierr, -6.0f, 6.0f) * PFC_TS;
    float duty = clampf(ierr * PFC_KPC + iint, 0.05f, 0.95f);

    return duty;
}

```

Figure 6. Implementation of the dual-loop control law.

2.3. Gate Driver PCB Design

To drive low-voltage PWM signals from the microcontroller to a high-voltage SiC switch, isolated gate driver stage was designed around the UCC21520DW dual-channel isolated driver (Figure 7). This device was selected for its high peak source and sink current, its galvanic isolation and its ability to drive SiC devices at high switching frequency with short, well-defined edges.

The converter and average current mode controller were simulated in LTspice using behavioral components to represent the two control loops (Figure 9). The PI gains for the two loops were set in the simulation: $K_{pv} = 0.04$ and $K_{iv} = 0.4$ for the external voltage loop, and $K_{pc} = 0.1$ and $K_{ic} = 5$ for the internal current loop; the control law was evaluated at a sampling period of $T_s = 0.05$ ms, corresponding to a switching frequency of 20 kHz.

Figure 9. Closed-loop simulation model of the proposed PFC boost converter.

Figure 10 shows the startup response: over a two-second startup window, the output voltage rises smoothly to 600 V with no overshoot, and the load current settles near the expected 3.33 A.

Figure 10. Start-up response output voltage rising to 600 V and load current settling near 3.33 A.

Figure 11 shows the steady state behavior. While the inductor current follows a rectified sinusoidal waveform, the output voltage ripple remains within a few percent of 600 V. The

shaped input current remains in phase with the line voltage, thus verifying that the simulation operates near unity power factor. This is the primary design objective. By aligning with the analytically calculated operating point, the simulation validates the inductor and capacitor sizing performed in Section 2.1.

Figure 11. Steady-state waveforms of the inductor current, output current and output voltage.

The isolated gate driver board was tested before being integrated into the circuit with the SiC MOSFET in converter. A 20 kHz PWM signal was used at the driver input. The gate driver output was monitored on oscilloscope and recorded in real time (Figure 12). It was observed that the output had the minimum 15 V amplitude required for switching. The observed frequency matched the 20 kHz reference frequency value. This confirmed that the driver was suitable for integration into the converter.

Figure 12. Measured gate-drive signals at 20 kHz.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the design of a microcontroller-based modular PFC boost converter with a nominal power of 2 kW and a DC output voltage of 600 V, controlled by average current mode control algorithm and manufactured silicon carbide semiconductors. The operating mode is set to CCM. Closed-loop simulation has verified operation with a power factor close to unity, a sinusoidal input current and a regulated, low-ripple output. The control algorithm has been implemented on an STM32 microcontroller and the isolated gate driver stage has been designed, fabricated and experimentally validated to operate at 20 kHz with a 15 V drive voltage required by the SiC device. Compared to a single high-power unit, the use of a modular architecture provides scalability to higher power levels and easier maintenance. SiC semiconductors play a critical role in minimizing switching losses in the circuit. The design is open to further structural improvements. It aims to contribute to industrial power supply and renewable energy applications.

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